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THE CHALLENGES OF PART-TIME WORK IN THE CONTEXT OF FLEXICURITY¹

Abstract:

Part-time work has become an important instrument of the national legislators to create new jobs and to respond to employers' demands for increased flexibility. For workers it can be a „bridge“ between employment and inactivity and vice versa, as well as an instrument to achieve a better balance between working life and family responsibilities. The law regulating atypical employment relationship has a complex role to play today: to promote the creation of the desired voluntary part-time work arrangements and to put those workers on equal footing with „standard“ workers. In Croatia only a small percentage of workers work part-time. Unlike workers in other EU member states, especially those with a lower unemployment rate, Croatian workers choose to work part-time mostly involuntarily in the absence of full-time employment opportunities. The authors analyse the advantages and disadvantages of part-time work, regulation of part-time work at the international and regional level with special attention to problem issues regarding definition and access to part-time work. In this context the case law of the European Court of Justice has been consulted. Measures encouraging part-time work, as well as good practice in some European countries have been presented. Also, they analyse problem related to low rate of part-time work in Croatia and propose solutions de lege ferenda.

Keywords: *part-time work, ILO Part-Time Work Convention (No. 175), Part-Time Work Directive, Croatian law, CJEU case law.*

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I. INTRODUCTION

The EU employment policy is most visibly articulated through the European Employment Strategy² (EES)³ as an open method of coordination process in existence since the late 1990s⁴, which as a rule favours a combination of flexibility⁵ and security (flexicurity)⁶. Flexicurity involves a combination of flexible and reliable contractual arrangements⁷,

² M. Biagi, 'The Impact of European Employment Strategy on the Role of Labour Law and Industrial Relations' in M. Tiraboschi (ed.), *Marco Biagi Selected Writings*, The Hague, Kluwer Law International, 2003, pp. 13-28.

³ The aim of the EES is threefold. First, the increase of the legitimacy of Community-level action by respecting to a greater degree the diversity of national industrial relations and labour market systems. Second, to improve the efficiency of Social Europe by achieving more and better results. The competition introduced with Maastricht Treaty between two basic rule-making methods (legislative and contractual) was supposed to enhance the efficiency of social regulation. Third, the EES was also intended to serve as a catalyst for the efficiency of national employment policies. J. Goetschy, 'The European Employment Strategy: Genesis and Development', *European Journal of Industrial Relations*, vol. 5, no. 2, 1999, pp. 130-133.

⁴ N. Bodiroga-Vukobrat, G. Sander and S. Barić (eds.), *Die Offene Methode der Koordinierung in der Europäischen Union / Open Method of Coordination in the European Union*, Hamburg, Verlag Dr. Kovač, 2010.

⁵ A decade ago the issue of labour market flexibility has become instrumental in the debate over labour market policy in Europe. The lack of dynamism in the flexibility of labour markets within EU countries, which was often characterised by a high share of long-term unemployment and strict employment protection legislation, has frequently been blamed for poor employment performance of the 1980s and 1990s. Atypical employment such as part-time work, self-employment and temporary employment could help to utilise untapped employment potential. H. Buddelmeyer, G. Mourre, and M. Ward-Warmedinger, 'Part-time work in EU countries (labour market mobility, entry and exit)', European Central Bank, *Working Paper Series*, No. 460, 2005, <https://www.ecb.europa.eu/pub/pdf/scpwps/ecbwp460.pdf>, (accessed 25 September 2015). A number of studies dealing with the labour market flexibility in the context of Monetary Union argue that flexibility has beneficial effect on employment, output and prices, improving prospects for jobs creation J. M. Abowd and F. Kramarz, 'The cost of hiring and separations', *National bureau of economic research working paper*, no. 6110, 1997; T. M. Andersen, N. Haldrup and J. R. Sørensen, 2000; 'Labour Market Implications of EU Product Market Integration', *Economic Policy*, vol. 30, pp. 107-133.; J. Haskel, B. Kersley and C. Martin, 'Labour market flexibility and employment adjustment: micro evidence from UK establishments', *Oxford Economic Papers, New Series*, vol. 49, no. 3, 1997, pp. 362-379; G. Saint-Paul and S. Bentolia, 'Will EMU increase Eurosclerosis?', *CERP Discussion paper*, no. 2423, 2000.

⁶ There has been a shift from a debate around the needs of market integration to one that focuses on the most appropriate forms of market regulation, that is finding the best mix between worker protection and economic freedom with a view to enhancing the European Union's competitiveness. A. Bilić, 'Transformacija radnopravnog odnosa', *Zbornik Pravnog fakulteta Sveučilišta u Rijeci*, vol. 32, no. 2, 2011, p. 755-794. This balance between economic and social considerations is now reflected in the Treaty's commitment to pursue a highly competitive social market economy. Article 3(3) of the Treaty on European Union.

⁷ A. Bilić, 'Fleksibilni oblici rada i radno pravo', *Zbornik Pravnog fakulteta Sveučilišta u Rijeci*, vol. 30, no. 2, 2009, pp. 920-942; A. Bilić, 'Ugovor o radu na određeno vrijeme – usklađivanje radnog zakonodavstva Republike Hrvatske sa propisima Europske unije', *Zbornik radova Pravnog fakulteta u Splitu*, vol. 41, 2004, pp. 167-18; I. Rozić, S. Jašarević and A. Bilić, 'Harmonizacija nacionalnog radnog prava s komunitarnim radnim pravom uz poseban osvrt na fleksibilne oblike zapošljavanja (Republika Hrvatska, Bosna i Hercegovina i Srbija)', *Zbornik radova Aktualnosti građanskog i trgovačkog zakonodavstva i pravne prakse*, no. 10, 2012, pp. 330-361.

comprehensive lifelong learning strategies, effective labour market policies and modern, adequate and sustainable social protection systems.⁸ The EES, thus put the spotlight on the growth of non-standard forms of work, in light of the risk that two-tier labour market was emerging divided between „insiders“ (standard work associated with full protection) and „outsiders“ (non standard work confronting greater precariousness).⁹

Among non-standard forms of work over the past 20 years there has been an increase¹⁰ in part-time employment, as opposed to full-time employment.¹¹

In most countries, part-time work is defined in relation to full-time working hours. Considering that full-time working hours can be calculated on a daily, weekly, monthly or even yearly basis as the average period of employment, there are many differences in national statistics in regard to what is considered full-time working hours. In consequence, a part-time worker in one country might be considered a full-time worker in another country.¹²

⁸ European Commission, Modernizing labour law to meet the challenges of the 21st Century, COM (2006)708, p. 4. More on lifelong learning strategies, effective labour market policies and sustainable social protection systems, in A. Bilić, 'Fleksibilnost i deregulacija u radnim odnosima', PhD Thesis, Sveučilište u Splitu, 2012, pp. 199-234.

⁹ In his study Tam finds that the boundary between the two markets divides the part-time working population. The shorter the hours worked, the worse off the part-time will be. Especially in the case of women, part-time work appears to be a factor that aggravates initial handicaps, such as low skill levels, and thereby weakens the worker's position on the labour market. Part-time work constitutes a trap which lowers woman's lifetime employment prospects and earnings. M. Tam, *Part-time employment: A bridge or trap?*, Avebury, Aldershot, 1997, pp. 240-243.

¹⁰ Factors affecting part-time rate are: access to childcare; differences in working hours cultures; quality of available part-time jobs and differences in legislation. E. Sandor, 'Part-time work in Europe', *European company survey*, European foundation for the improvement of living and working conditions, 2009, p.13.

¹¹ In 2012 the part-time work in EU amounted to 19.8%. Part-time employment was stable from 2013 to 2014 (20.6 %). In 2014, the share of employees working part-time was highest in the Netherlands (52.4 % of employees), followed by Germany (28.3 %), Austria (27.7 %), Denmark (26.3%) and the United Kingdom and Sweden (both 26.2 %). The lowest shares were recorded in Romania (0.7 %), Bulgaria (2.1 %), Croatia (3.0 %), Slovakia (5.7 %) and Latvia (5.9 %). Two EFTA countries, Switzerland (37.4 %) and Norway (26.5 %), also had a relatively large share of part-time employees. http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Labour_market_and_Labour_force_survey_%28LFS%29_statistics, (accessed 25 September 2015).

¹² In countries where part-time work is common, the number of jobs of more than 30 usual hours per week that are classified as part-time are significant. These countries tend to use a definition based on a 35 usual hours threshold. In countries where part-time work is relatively less common, the incidence of jobs of less than 35 usual hours per week that are classified as full-time is high. Part-time jobs are generally identified on the basis of self-assessment in these countries. There is less variability among countries in the incidence of part-time work when the latter is defined by a threshold (30 or 35 usual hours) than when the national definitions are used. Application of a uniform threshold across countries does not substantially change the relative position of countries regarding the frequency of part-time work. A. Bastelaer van, G. Lemaitre and P. Marianna, 'The definition of part-time work for the purpose of international comparisons', *OECD Labour market and social policy occasional papers*, no. 22, 1997, p. 12, <https://is.muni.cz/repo/1301291/5lgs-jhv7t7c.pdf> (accessed 28 September 2015).

In Croatia only a small percentage of workers work part-time.¹³ In general, workers in Croatia are not very interested in shortening their working hours and earnings because the low level of wages means that any wage reduction has an impact on the household budget.

Employers also prefer full-time employment claiming that part-time contracts do not usually bring sufficient cost reduction to counterbalance the negative effect of the unavailability of part-time employees to their colleagues and clients during regular working hours, while job sharing in fact poses additional costs. Unlike workers in other EU member states, especially those with a lower unemployment rate, Croatian workers choose to work part-time mostly involuntarily in the absence of full-time employment opportunities.

The share of involuntary part-time work has been higher than 40%. Indeed, faced with financial problems many enterprises turn to shorter working hours of all or certain categories of workers to bridge this difficult period. Croatia has experienced a certain increase in the share of part-time employment within total employment. Despite the high unemployment rate (17,2%) in Croatia, only about 8.7% of total employed persons work less than full time, from which it can be concluded that this institute is still rarely used. Of the total employed persons working part-time, 11.1 % are woman and 6.8% are men.

A vast majority of part-time workers are employed by small and medium-sized enterprises, predominately in the sector of education (both elementary and secondary), then in agriculture, followed by the administrative, services sector, financial and insurance sector, and at least in industrial activities. Instead of concluding a part-time contract, employers very often use service contract (contract for work), mostly illegal, since it is concluded for the work with characteristics of employment.¹⁴

In Croatia woman workers are overrepresented among part-time workers. A more frequent incidence of part-time work among woman is connected with their primary responsibility for childcare and care for the elderly that is still rarely done by men, whereas this arrangement enables them to combine employment with family responsibilities. Moreover, a combination of part-time employment and maternity/parental leave without losing entitlement to allowances is utilised quite often.¹⁵

In this article the authors analyse pertinent issues concerning part-time work: the advantages and disadvantages of part-time work, its regulation at the international and EU

¹³ According to statistical data provided by the Croatian Pension Insurance Fund for 2012, 73.000 of the obligatory insured persons were part-time workers. Among them 45.400 were employed by two or more employers, therefore in fact should be considered full-time employees. <http://rasprava.mrms.hr/bill/nacrt-prijedloga-iskaz-zakon-o-radu/1/1/1>, (accessed 16 October 2014)

¹⁴ M. Zuber, 'Rad u nepunom radnom vremenu', *Računovodstvo i financije*, vol. 50, no. 5, 2004, p. 44.

¹⁵ A. Bilić, 'Ravnopravnost spolova u kontekstu fleksibilnih oblika rada', in Ž. Potočnjak, (ed.), *Perspektive antidiskriminacijskog prava*, Zagreb, Pravni fakultet Zagreb, 2014, p. 129.

level, Croatian legislation and prospects regarding part-time work, part-time work in relation to „very atypical work“, relevant case-law of the CJEU and measures encouraging part-time work. In conclusion, the authors make proposals *de lege ferenda*.

II. PART-TIME WORK AS A NON-STANDARD FORM OF WORK

The following factors can be singled out as the determinants of part-time work: household composition regarding the probability of working part-time for both males and females; country specific arrangements that may strongly influence individual decisions to work part time; the effect of past labour market history, which has a significant impact on the current labour market state for both men and women and the firms' behaviour^{16, 17} In this respect it is crucial that the family as an institution be considered central to the understanding of labour market reforms. If social policy is leading to „de-familialisation“ or detachment from the family, than more weight is put on the state for the provision of services otherwise assigned to families. Accordingly, family support may very well channel the choice of unemployed people towards non-standard forms of work.¹⁸

Indeed, there has been much public praise of its supposed merits in reducing unemployment and of its benefits for workers and employers alike.¹⁹

2.1. Advantages of part-time work

Part-time work offers workers a better balance between working life and family responsibilities, training, leisure or civic activities.²⁰ The most striking feature of part-time work is its gendered nature, as women prevail among those working part-time. Pursuant

¹⁶ Buddelmeyer et al., Part-time work, pp. 5, 6.

¹⁷ The differences in the diffusion of part-time employment at the national level could be explained by differences among European countries as regards labour market regulations, extension of market activities relying on the use of part-time employment, tax and social security systems, economic situation, availability and organization of childcare provision, and cultures. J. O'Reilly and C. Fagan (eds.), *Part-time prospects: An international comparison of part-time work in Europe, North America and the Pacific*, Routledge, 1998.

¹⁸ S. Schiarra, 'New discourses in labour law: part-time work and the paradigm of flexibility', in S. Schiarra, P. Davies and M. Freedland (eds.), *Employment Policy and the Regulation of Part-time Work in the European Union (A Comparative Analysis)*, New York, Cambridge University Press, 2011, p. 10.

¹⁹ H. Buddelmeyer, G. Mourre and M. Ward, 'Recent developments in part-time work in EU-15 countries: trends and policy', *Discussion Paper Series*, Forschungsinstitut zur Zukunft der Arbeit, no. 1415, 2004, p. 5; H. Buddelmeyer, G. Mourre and M. Ward, 'Why do Europeans work part-time? A cross-country panel analysis', European central bank, *Working paper series*, no. 872, 2008, p. 5.

²⁰ Sandor, pp. 6-8.

to a 2014 statistics, 20.6 % workers worked part-time in the European Union, whereas three out of four employees working part-time in the EU were women (77.3 %).²¹ This trend can be witnessed across geographically and culturally diverse countries. This is not surprising in light of the fact that women remain the main care providers - whether in terms of raising children or looking after older relatives and part-time work is a means of allowing women to combine caring responsibilities with paid employment.

Furthermore, part-time work can also make it easier for workers to enter the labour market or retire from employment.²² One of the supposed virtues of part-time work is namely, that it facilitates a gradual entry of young persons into the labour market and enables older workers to gradually withdraw from employment. As regards the proportion of part-time work in older age groups of workers, various early retirement schemes²³ have been developed often in response to high unemployment or to avoid redundancies during restructuring accompanied with financial help from the state or unemployment insurance funds. At the enterprise level, however, such arrangements can cause a sudden loss of skills and experience.²⁴ For this reason, a number of countries such as Belgium, France, Portugal and Spain were promoting gradual retirement by offering older workers part-time work, while encouraging employers to hire young persons also on a part-time basis, thus enabling experienced workers to pass on their skills to beginners.²⁵ Part-time

²¹ http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Labour_market_and_Labour_force_survey_%28LFS%29_statistics (accessed 25 September 2015)

²² L. Delsen, 'Part-time early retirement in Europe', *The Geneva papers on risk and insurance*, vol. 15, no. 55, April, 1990, pp. 139-157.

²³ These schemes may be applied to the national, sectoral or enterprise level. Part-time early retirement schemes give to older workers the freedom of choice and flexibility with regard to when and how they prefer to retire. This gradual transition to complete retirement contributes to the humanisation of work. These schemes may also improve the employment situation by sharing available jobs between a large number of people as a means of reducing unemployment. Delsen, p. 140.

²⁴ Early retirement schemes were initiated by employers. The main aim was to reduce the total early retirement costs and to retain knowledge and experience of older workers. Offering part-time work is a way of gaining access to a wider labour market or relevantly skilled workers, thus avoiding recruitment and training-related difficulties. Every economic growth contributes to the success of part-time early retirement. Delsen, p. 152. Due to the changed economic and demographic circumstances (ageing population, retirement of the baby-boom population, economic and financial crisis, slow economic growth, budget deficit and low employment) the EC White Paper (An Agenda for Adequate, Safe and Sustainable Pensions) 2012, emphasises the need to develop and put in place comprehensive strategies to adapt current EU Member States pension systems. „Pension reforms aimed at keeping people longer on the labour market also need to focus on removing unwarranted early retirement options which may apply to all employees or to specific professions... Whenever early retirement options are eliminated, it is important to ensure that the individuals concerned are enabled to work longer or, if this is not possible, can enjoy adequate income security.“ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=COM:2012:0055:FIN:EN:PDE>, (accessed at 5 September 2015), p. 11. For Croatian legislation, see S. Baloković, 'Starosna mirovina u hrvatskom mirovinskom osiguranju', *Radno pravo*, no. 7-8, 2014, p. 40-45.

²⁵ Contrary to full-time retirement schemes, none of the national schemes gives employees the right to part-time early retirement. Partial early retirement has to be a result of agreement between employer and

work makes it easier to reconcile family responsibilities with employment, with the added advantage of maintaining a link with working life and thus avoiding a total break as in the case of parental leave, which can create problems as regards subsequent skills upgrading.²⁶ In fact, it is within these three worker categories: youth, older workers and those with family responsibilities that part-time work prevails. Therefore, from the worker's point of view, part-time employment fulfils two main functions: that of a "bridge" between employment and inactivity and *vice versa*²⁷, and that of reconciling paid work and family responsibilities. The paradigm of women combining work with care responsibilities remains the dominant one, while an approach based exclusively on gender equality law marginalizes other types of part-time workers.²⁸ However, it is necessary to add that part-time work gives a chance to another vulnerable group of workers, i.e. workers with disabilities or certain illnesses, to join the world of work.

On the other side, by using part-time work the employers not only respond to market requirements with greater flexibility (e.g. by increasing capacity utilization or extending opening hours), but also increase productivity gains. That said, in the circumstances of economic change or crisis and consequently the need for greater flexibility, part-time work is a means for the employer to cope with extra workloads not requiring full-time workers, as well as to adjust working and opening hours in the retail trade, for example.²⁹ Some studies found that the hourly productivity of part-time workers is often higher.³⁰ The plausible explanations for this are that part-time employees work more intense; are as a rule less absent from work and less worn-out, and that "part-time workers, especially when they formerly worked full time, may be expected to carry out a set of activities that normally would be carried out by a full-time worker"³¹

employee. The Swedish partial pension scheme is financed by a pay-roll tax and in Germany by the employer. In Germany full retirement schemes was replaced by the part-time early retirement scheme and in all others European countries exists parallel to a full early retirement system. Delsen, p. 140-141.

²⁶ D. G. Tremblay and É. Genin, 'Parental leave: An important employee right, but an organizational challenge', *Employ respons rights*, no. 23, 2011, p. 258.

²⁷ J. O'Reilly and S. Bothfeld, 'What happens after working part-time? Integration, maintenance or exclusionary transitions in Britain and Western Germany', *Cambridge Journal of Economics*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 409ff.

²⁸ M. Bell, 'Achieving the objectives of the part-time work Directive? Revisiting the part-time workers regulations', *Industrial Law Journal*, vol. 40, no. 3, 2011, p. 279.

²⁹ Buddelmeyer et al., Recent developments, p. 28.

³⁰ A. Cataldi, S. Kampelman and F. Rycx, 'Part-time Work, Wages and Productivity: Evidence from Matched Panel Data', <http://www.sole-jole.org/12382.pdf> (accessed 2 October 2015); L. Golden, 'The effects of working time on productivity and firm performance: a research synthesis paper', International Labour Office, Geneva, Conditions of work and employment series, no. 33, 2011, pp. 6-7.

³¹ International Labour Office, *Part-time work*. Report V (1), International Labour Conference, 80th Session, Geneva, 1993, p. 40.

The growth of part-time work is of vital importance for policy-makers confronted with high unemployment, like those in Croatia. Resorting to part-time work may reduce the number of jobseekers³² and in turn lower politically-sensitive unemployment rates without requiring an increase in the total number of working hours.³³ It is worth mentioning here that when active employment policies are required to increase the employment rates, it has to be specified at the national level that new jobs should not be created under deregulatory regimes nor violate fundamental rights.³⁴

As Bell stressed, part-time work falls under the umbrella of precarious work, though it is not always evident why. Compared to fixed-term work, part-time work is not necessarily insecure regarding its duration. Moreover, contrary to agency work,³⁵ part-time workers often have a clear contractual relationship with the provider of employment.³⁶ Nonetheless, part-time work has its drawbacks.

2.2. Disadvantages of part-time work

Working part-time carries certain disadvantages for workers in comparison with their colleagues who perform equivalent work full time.³⁷ According to an ILO study,³⁸ their

³² New institutional economists argue that there are benefits for employers in the provision of part-time jobs. The reasons are partly macroeconomic, i.e. to use the country's labour resources to the full. At the micro-economic level, firms get access to a wider pool of talent from which they could recruit their employees. But the part-time jobs have to be sufficiently attractive. A.C.L. Davies, *Perspectives on Labour Law*, New York, Cambridge University Press, 2004, p. 6.

³³ F. Bönker and H. Wollmann, 'Stumbling towards reform: the German welfare state in the 1990s', in: P. Taylor-Gooby (ed.), *Welfare states under pressure*, London, Sage Publications, 1990, pp. 75-99; C. Fagan, *Working-time preferences and work-life balance in the EU: Some policy considerations for enhancing the quality of life*, Dublin, European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions, 2003, p. 14.

³⁴ S. Schiarra, *New Discourses*, p. 11.

³⁵ For Croatian legislation, see in S. Laleta and A. Križanović, 'Rad putem agencija za privremeno zapošljavanje u hrvatskom, europskom i usporednom pravu', *Zbornik Pravnog fakulteta Sveučilišta u Rijeci*, vol. 36, no. 1, 2015, pp. 305-340.

³⁶ M. Bell, 'Strengthening the protection of precarious workers: part-time workers', International Training Centre, International Labour Office, p. 2.; http://www.google.hr/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&ved=0ahUKewiH0KLOIK7JAhXMNxxQKHAYjDLsQFggZMAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fctrav-courses.itcilo.org%2Ffen%2Fa4-54332%2Fa4-54332-resources%2Ffitc-ilo-precarious-work%2Fstrengthening-the-protection-of-precarious-workers-part-time-workers%2Fat_download%2Ffile&usg=AFQjCNEBj_3Nd1MzYCBAOkJd2Ku7eIw6JA&sig2=SIHkaPc_xoQcVYGKA1Ninw (accessed 15 October 2015)

³⁷ The European working conditions survey (EWCS), a tool originally set up to help the improvement of quality of work in Europe, defines key dimensions of quality of work and employment as: career and employment security; health and well-being; skills development; reconciling work-life balance.

³⁸ P. Bollé, 'Part-time work: Solution or trap?' *International Labour Review*, vol. 136, no. 4, 1997, <http://www.ilo.org/public/english/revue/articles/97-4.htm>, (accessed at 5 May 2015).

hourly wages are typically lower³⁹ and their career prospects more limited⁴⁰. Likewise, their access to training and skill development opportunities are less favourable.⁴¹

Moreover, part-time workers are ineligible for certain social benefits. Working part-time often means less contribution to pensions based on workers' contributions, which consequently results in lower pensions and causes the gender pension gap.⁴²

Difficulties for part-time workers in relation to social security requirements were also identified in a research done by the ILO. In its survey of maternity rights (1999) it found that female part-time workers 'may have difficulty meeting the eligibility requirements for benefits in the form of time-in-service requirements or minimum periods of contribution which may take the part-time worker much longer to fulfil than a full-time worker. In this way, a large number of women workers may fall outside of maternity protection.'⁴³

³⁹ Most of the full-time/part-time wage in hourly wages is driven by sex segregation. E. Matteazzi, A. Pailhé and A. Solaz, 'Part-time wage penalties in Europe: a matter of selection or segregation?' *ECINEQ, working paper series*, no. 250, 2012, p. 26, <http://www.ecineq.org/milano/WP/ECINEQ2012-250.pdf> (accessed 12 September 2015); M. Jepsen et al., 'The wage penalty induced by part-time work: the case of Belgium', *Brussels Economic Review*, vol. 48, no. 1-2, pp. 73-94; D. Fernández-Kranz and N. Rodríguez-Planas, 'The part-time pay penalty in a segmented labour market', *IZA DP*, no. 4342, 2009, <http://ftp.iza.org/dp4342.pdf>, (accessed 23 October 2015); A. Manning and B. Petrongolo, B., 'The part-time penalty for woman in Britain', *The Economic Journal*, vol. 118, no. 526, 2008, pp. 28-51; E. Bardasi and J. Gornick 'Working for less? Women's part-time wage penalties across countries', *Feminist Economics*, vol. 14, no. 1, 2009, pp. 37-72.

⁴⁰ On average, part-time workers are less likely to feel that their job offers good prospects for career advancement. Analysis by the number of hours worked per week shows that employees working between 41 and 50 hours are optimistic about their career prospects (34%), followed by those working 31 to 40 hours (32%). Those working less are significantly less likely to say they have good opportunities for promotion, and this proportion decreases in line with the number of hours worked. Sandor, p. 5.

⁴¹ C. Lyonette, B. Baldauf and H. Behle, *Quality part-time work: A review of the evidence*, London, Government Equalities Office, Institute for Employment Research, University of Warwick, Coventry, 2010, p. 56-59.

⁴² S. Burri and H. Aune, *Sex Discrimination in Relation to Part-Time and Fixed-Term Work, The application of EU and national law in practice in 33 European countries*, European Union, 2013, p. 23. "Unless mechanisms are in place to ensure social security coverage for non-standard workers through an extension of contributory or non-contributory social security mechanisms, these workers are more likely to be inadequately covered or not covered at all and are, as a result, more exposed to social risks than other workers, including with respect to income security and effective access to health care." International Labour Office, *Non-standard forms of employment*, Report for discussion at the Meeting of Experts on Non-Standard Forms of Employment, Geneva, 16–19 February 2015, p. 27, http://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_protect/---protrav/---travail/documents/meetingdocument/wcms_336934.pdf, (accessed 3 September 2015); International Labour Office, *World Social Protection Report 2014/15: Building economic recovery, inclusive development and social justice*, Geneva, http://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---dcomm/documents/publication/wcms_245201.pdf, (accessed 3 September 2015). Also: S. Houseman and M. Osawa, 'What is the nature of the part-time work in the United States and Japan?' in J. O'Reilly and C. Fagan (eds.), *Part-time prospects: An international comparison of part-time work in Europe, North America and the Pacific*, London, Routledge, 1998, pp. 232-251.

⁴³ International Labour Office, 'Maternity protection at work. Report V(1); International Labour Conference, 87th session, 1999, chapter 2.

Besides, unless working part time is voluntary, it may leave them only marginally better off than if they were unemployed.⁴⁴ Part-time workers are also at a disadvantage because of their hours of work. In the case of overtime work, part-time worker often receives premium payments for overtime only after he/she has worked the normal full-time hours. Here the overtime is used as a means of achieving flexibility by employing part-time workers on relatively short basic hours and requesting them to work substantial overtime during peak periods. Some laws or collective agreements prescribe that overtime rates apply once the normal working hours of part-time worker have been exceeded. Nevertheless, their provisions do specify a maximum of overtime hours with the view of avoiding discrepancies between part-time and full-time labour costs.

As previously said part-time workers are on average paid lower hourly rates than full-time workers.⁴⁵ This is the case even with respect to equivalent work performed within the same establishment. However, the difference is even more apparent when considering groups of workers. A number of factors are relevant in this context: part-time workers “tend to work in sectors and indeed in branches of sectors where the hourly rates of pay are low in comparison with the national average. They also tend to be employed in low-graded jobs and to be excluded from supervisory posts.”⁴⁶ Workers who work part-time are more likely to be excluded from supplementary payments (bonuses, holiday and sickness pay, training allowances, seniority payments, etc.). In addition, one of very important questions is that of the minimum number of hours of work required to qualify for certain entitlements, as in the case of redundancy pay or other benefits.⁴⁷

The precariousness of part-time work results in a weaker level of part-timers’ collective organisation.⁴⁸ According to the ILO 2004 global report there were lower rates of unionisation amongst part-time workers,⁴⁹ which has been partially attributed to the

⁴⁴ P. Bollé, p. 1.

⁴⁵ C. Fagan and J. O’Reilly, ‘Conceptualising part-time work: the value of an integrated comparative perspective’, in: J. O’Reilly and C. Fagan, (eds.), *Part-time prospects*, pp. 1-31; J. C. Gornick and J. A. Jacobs, ‘A cross national analysis of the wages of part-time workers: evidence from the United States, the United Kingdom, Canada and Australia’, *Work, Employment and Society*, vol. 10, no. 1, 1996, pp. 1-27; F. McGinnity and P. McManus, ‘Paying the price for reconciling work and family life: comparing the wage penalty for women’s part-time work in Britain, Germany and the United States’, *Journal of comparative policy analysis: research and practice*, vol. 9, no. 2, 2007, pp. 115-234.

⁴⁶ International Labour Office, *Part-time work*, 1993, p. 34.

⁴⁷ P. Bollé, cit.

⁴⁸ Bell, *Strengthening the protection*, p. 5.

⁴⁹ International Labour Office, *Organising for social justice. Global report under the follow-up to the ILO Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work*, International Labour Conference 92nd session, report I(B), 2004, p. 53. In the UK, only 22% of part-timers are trade union members (in the private sector only 10%) comparing to 30% of full-time employees. J. Achur, *Trade union membership 2009*, London, Department for Business, Innovation and Skills, 2010, p. 15. One of the arguments is the specific trade unions’ approach to part-time workers, i.e. in the past, recruitment of these workers has been perceived as

prevalent number of part-time workers in occupations with lower levels of trade-union membership in general.⁵⁰

Bell reiterates that the gendered nature of part-time work is a central reason for its devaluation within the labour market.⁵¹ The ILO's 2007 global report concluded that: 'in most countries part-time work remains women's work and is synonymous with low status, low training and limited career opportunities, despite its being often presented as available to both working mothers and fathers. Moreover, part-time may often be involuntary, in the sense that it is a second-best option to a full-time job.'⁵²

Part-timers who work "on call", on the "zero hours" system (without any guaranteed minimum weekly or monthly number of hours) are in a particularly vulnerable situation. They cannot rely on a minimum income, and are often excluded from certain rights and benefits, or entitlement which is subject to a minimum number of hours worked.⁵³

From the employers' point of view, part-time work has for a long time presented more disadvantages than advantages. For one thing, it increases costs (e.g. for fixed recruitment and training costs per employee and social security contributions) and, on the other hand, complicates work organization (e.g. co-ordination among part-time employees).

Likewise, involuntary part-time work (i.e. work done by people who would prefer a full time job) amounts to underemployment in macroeconomic and macrosocial terms.

There are two main categories of involuntary part-time work: individuals who work part-time due to a lack of work or unfavorable business conditions and individuals who could only find part-time work.⁵⁴ Involuntary part-time work can weaken demand, and consequently have negative effects on growth and in turn employment.

EU statistics confirm the view that part-time work is sometimes involuntary because of a lack of adequate childcare facilities. In 2008, around 30% of women were economically inactive or working part-time as a result of the lack of care services for children and other dependents. Because of women's caring responsibilities, they are often unable to

less important. S. Walters, 'Female part-time workers' attitudes to trade unions in Britain', *British Journal of Industrial Relations*, vol. 40, 2002, pp. 49, 50, both cited in Bell, Strengthening the protection, p. 5.

⁵⁰ Walters, p. 5.

⁵¹ Bell, Strengthening the protection, p. 4.

⁵² International Labour Office, *Equality at work: tackling the challenges. Global report under the follow-up to the ILO Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work*, International Labour Conference 96th session, report I(B), 2007, p. 78. http://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---dcomm/---webdev/documents/publication/wcms_082607.pdf (accessed 10 September 2015)

⁵³ International Labour Office, *Part-time work*, 1993, p. 16.

⁵⁴ T. Cajner et al., 'Why is involuntary part-time work elevated?' <http://www.federalreserve.gov/econresdata/notes/feds-notes/2014/why-is-involuntary-part-time-work-elevated-20140414.html>, (accessed 15 September 2015)

work full-time (especially if it means long and antisocial working hours). Part-time work tends to be frequent in the low status parts of the labour market, which can result in women working below the level of their qualifications and/or professional experience.⁵⁵ As a result of a disproportionate share of women with family responsibilities and difficulties in reconciling work with private life, many work part-time or under atypical contracts.⁵⁶

III. REGULATION OF PART-TIME WORK AT THE INTERNATIONAL AND REGIONAL LEVEL

Irrespective of the above mentioned disadvantages, part-time work has been increasingly considered a positive instrument for promoting employment and facilitating the reconciliation of work and family life. In encouraging its growth and improving its quality, the labour market regulation is faced with the difficulty of achieving a balance. „Measures to encourage employers to use part-time work might lead in the direction of deregulation, whereas steps to combat the disadvantages experienced by part-time workers tend to require legal intervention. In this respect, part-time work is a good example of the crossroads between flexible labour markets and protecting social rights.“⁵⁷

The increase in part-time employment and the difficulties associated with it attracted much attention and in turn led to the adoption of two important regulatory instruments. At the international level in 1994 the ILO has adopted the Part-Time Work Convention (No. 175) and Recommendation (No. 182). At the European level the social partners of the

⁵⁵ Bell, *Strengthening the protection*, p. 4; European Commission, *Report on equality between women and men – 2010*, Luxembourg, Publications Office of the European Union, 2010, p. 40. http://www.google.hr/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&ved=0ahUKEwjx8OrkK7JAhXlUhQKHe45COAQFggZMAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fec.europa.eu%2Fsocial%2FBlobServlet%3FdocId%3D4613%26langId%3Den&usg=AFQjCNGnQct1C61Dv_wDNHIR4yyuDbUnKg&sig2=uqAmTINXe256CRjBU5rZRQ, (accessed 22 September 2015); European Commission, *Gender segregation in the labour market – root causes, implications and policy responses in the EU*, Luxembourg, Publications Office of the European Union, 2009, p. 43.

⁵⁶ This permits them to remain in the labour market while managing family responsibilities, but consequently can have a negative impact on their pay, career development, promotion prospects and pensions. European Commission, *Strategy for equality between women and men 2010-2015*, http://ec.europa.eu/justice/gender-equality/files/strategy_equality_women_men_en.pdf, (accessed 25 October 2015). The European Union released its new framework *Gender equality and women's empowerment: transforming the lives of girls and women through EU external relations 2016-2020* – the new EU Gender Action Plan (GAP) for 2016-2020, on 21 of September 2016. It was the answer to 2010-2015 GAP's weak institutional leadership, accountability and capacity. See more H. O'Connell, 'The European Union's new Gender Action Plan 2016-2020 (Gender equality and women's empowerment in external relations)', <http://www.odi.org/sites/odi.org.uk/files/odi-assets/publications-opinion-files/9926.pdf>, (accessed 24 November 2015)

⁵⁷ Bell, *Strengthening the protection*, p. 5.

European Union signed in 1997 the Framework Agreement on part-time work,⁵⁸ which was later upgraded into a Directive.⁵⁹

The objectives of the Convention and Part-Time Workers' Directive are: removal of discrimination against part-time workers; improvement of quality of part-time work; development of part-time work on a voluntary basis; contribution to the flexible organisation of working time in a manner which takes into account the needs of employers and workers.

The Part-Time Work Convention of 1994 (No. 175) aims at promoting access to productive and freely chosen part-time work that meets the needs of both employers and workers, and ensuring protection for part-time workers with respect to access to employment, working conditions and social security.

The Convention applies to all part-time workers – defined as employed persons whose normal hours of work are fewer than those of comparable full-time workers. The Convention seeks to ensure equal treatment of part-time workers and comparable full-time workers in a variety of ways. First, part-time workers are to be granted the same protection as comparable full-time workers in relation to the right to organize, the right to bargain collectively and the right to worker representatives; occupational safety and health; and discrimination in employment and occupation. Second, measures must be taken to ensure that part-time workers do not, solely because they work part-time, receive a basic wage which, calculated proportionately, is lower than that of comparable full-time workers. Third, statutory social security schemes based on occupational activity should be adapted so that part-time workers enjoy conditions equivalent to those of comparable full-time workers, and these conditions may be determined in proportion to hours of work, contributions or earnings. Fourth, part-time workers must also enjoy equivalent conditions with respect to maternity protection, termination of employment, paid annual leave and paid public holidays, and sick leave. The Convention also calls for the adoption of measures to facilitate access to productive and freely chosen part-time work which meets the needs of both employers and workers, provided that the required protection, as mentioned above, is ensured. It also provides that measures must be taken, where appropriate, to ensure that transfer from full-time to part-time work or *vice versa* is voluntary, in accordance with national law and practice.⁶⁰

⁵⁸ Its parties are the European Trade Union Confederation (ETUC), the Union of Industrial and Employers' Confederations of Europe (UNICE) and the European Centre of Enterprises with Public Participation (CEEP).

⁵⁹ Council Directive 97/81/EC of 15 December 1997 concerning the Framework Agreement on part-time work concluded by UNICE, CEEP and the ETUC, OJ L 014, 20/01/1998, P. 0009 – 0014.

⁶⁰ N. Valticos and G. von Potobsky, *International labour law*, Boston, Kluwer Law and Taxation Publishers, 1995, pp. 166-167.

As regards the EU level, the Part-Time Directive reflects a trade-off between flexibility of working time and standards on the treatment of part-time workers. This is most evident in the form of obligation imposed on the Member States and social partners to „identify and review“ obstacles to part-time working. So, the purpose of Directive is to: a) provide for the removal of discrimination against part-time workers and to improve the quality of part-time work; b) facilitate the development of part-time work on a voluntary basis and to contribute to the flexible organisation of working time in a manner which takes into account the needs of employers and workers.⁶¹

Consequently, when regulating part-time work, Member States have to pursue: worker's protection, employment promotion and flexibilisation of work relations, support of part-time work. This can be realised by both soft and hard law instruments.

In view of the application of the principle of non-discrimination of part-time workers in practice, we must examine the definition of a part-time worker and access to part-time work.

3.1. Problems related to the definition of a part-time worker

Both the Convention and the Directive provide a similar definition of the term 'part-time worker'. According to the Art. 1a) Convention No. 175 "the term 'part-time worker' means an employed person whose normal hours of work are less than those of comparable full-time workers". The reason why the concept of a "comparable" worker is mentioned is that "the number of hours per week or per month that are regarded as being normal for full-time employees vary considerably according to the profession or activity concerned". Concerning hours of work, Convention No. 175 states that these may be calculated weekly or on average over a given period of employment. Similarly, the Directive offers the following definition: "The term 'part-time worker' refers to an employee whose normal hours of work, calculated on a weekly basis or on average over a period of employment of up to one year, are less than the normal hours of work of a comparable full-time worker" (Clause 3/1).

The Framework Agreement intends to contribute to the EES on employment and to combat discrimination against part-time workers. The notion of comparable full-time worker is introduced as a means to define the part-timer. The main implication of the principle of non-discrimination is the ban on less favourable treatment of part-timers as compared to full-timers within the same establishment, or where such worker does not exist, with reference to collective agreement or other national sources. Exemption could

⁶¹ Clause 1.

be made if justified on objective grounds, and recourse, whenever possible, to the principle of *pro rata temporis*.⁶²

Using comparators is a common method for identifying discrimination. However, the requirement for a comparator presents numerous difficulties for the practical implementation of both the Convention and the Framework Agreement. The biggest problem is that most EU anti-discrimination legislation leaves the courts considerable flexibility⁶³ identifying the appropriate comparator which allows the courts, for example, to have recourse to a hypothetical comparator where no actual comparator can be identified.

Also, for claimants it will be difficult to prove that they enjoy the same 'type' of employment relationship and perform 'the same or a similar type of work'. Compared to full-time workers, part-time workers are present in the workplace for a smaller number of hours per week and consequently full-time workers have a wider range of tasks and responsibilities. The employers may object that the type of work performed is sufficiently different in order to render the workers not comparable.⁶⁴

Another observation to be made here is that the requirement for comparability is likely to lower the possibility for casual workers⁶⁵ to rely on the Convention.⁶⁶ Art. 3(1) of the

⁶² S. Schiarra, 'New Discourses in Labour Law (Part-time Work and the Paradigm of Flexibility)', *EUI Working Paper LAW*, No. 2003/14, Florence, European University Institute, 2003, p. 20-22, <http://cadmus.eui.eu/bitstream/handle/1814/1868/law03-14.pdf?sequence=1> (accessed 30 September 2015). For example, the annual leave entitlement of a worker who works 3 days per week would be 60% of that of a full-time worker who works 5 days per week. The definition of 'comparable full-time worker' is very similar to that found in Convention 175.

⁶³ M. Bell has identified some initial trends. The Court of Justice has rejected the idea that the principle of equal treatment should be interpreted in a highly flexible manner (Case C144/04 Mangold [2005] ECR I-9981, para. 42, 43. Further, it has supported a broad interpretation of material scope of the prohibition of discrimination (Case C-396/08 INPS v Bruno and Pettini, *INPS v Lotti and Matteucci*[2010]). There is a Courts' tendency to minimise the flexibility within the principle of equal treatment relates to the scope for objective justification for difference in treatment. That concept requires the unequal treatment at issue to be justified by the existence of precise and concrete factors on the basis of objective and transparent criteria in order to ensure that that unequal treatment in fact responds to a genuine need, is appropriate for achieving the objective pursued and is necessary for that purpose. Case C-307/05 *Del Cerro Alonso* [2007] ECR I-7109 para. 57 – 58.

⁶⁴ Bell, *Strengthening the protection*, p. 11. The author finds the illustration of this argument in the case of *Matthews and others v Kent and Medway Towns Fire Authority*. The case concerned part-time fire fighters (so called 'retained' fire fighters) and their exclusion from an occupational pension scheme that was open to full-time fire fighters. The employer argued that the part-time fire fighters mainly provided emergency work (i.e. responding to fires), whereas full-time fire fighters also undertook educational and safety inspection work. The relevant English legislation required part-time workers to demonstrate that they had the same type of employment contract and performed similar work to the full-time comparator.

⁶⁵ See *infra* chapter 5.

⁶⁶ L. Vosko, 'Gender, precarious work, and the International Labour Code: the ghost in the ILO closet' in J. Fudge and R. Owens (eds.), *Precarious work, women, and the new economy – the challenge to legal norms*, Oxford, Hart Publishing, 2006, pp. 53, 61 in Bell, *Strengthening the protection*, p. 11.

Convention enables Member States to exclude this type of worker from its scope. But even if they are covered by the Convention, „the requirement to show that they have the ‘same type of employment relationship’ is likely to limit the Convention’s utility“.⁶⁷

Another hurdle for part-time worker could emerge in situations in which there is no full-time worker to be compared to the part-timer. As previously mentioned, part-time work tends to be concentrated in low status sectors of the economy and lower grade occupations within an enterprise. According to Article 1(c)(iii) it is possible to find a comparator outside the enterprise, ‘in the same branch of activity’. Bell suggests a more flexible approach by allowing hypothetical comparators as in the English case of *Royal Mail Group plc v Lynch*.⁶⁸

Also, there is abundant evidence demonstrating that the Part-Time Work Directive (and also other directives on atypical work) is primarily based on the flexicurity approach. On the other hand, the Court of Justice has in its initial case law adopted a relatively rigorous interpretation of the principle of equal treatment that places little emphasis on flexicurity and the reason is the use of the comparator test. According to the latter, only those non-standard workers whose employment relationship is relatively proximate to the standard worker are able to access the benefits of the principle of equal treatment.⁶⁹ This

⁶⁷ Bell, Strengthening the protection, p. 12 As Bell points out in Case C-313/02 *Wippel* [2004] ECR I-9483, the Court of Justice concluded that even if the claimant fell within the scope of the EU Framework Agreement on Part-Time Work, she could not be treated as comparable to a full-time worker because she had no fixed working hours and she had the possibility to refuse work if she did not wish to do it. For more on this case see infra note 70.

⁶⁸ In this case the claimant was a part-time worker. She was successful in applying for a full-time position within the same enterprise. The employer had a policy that an internal job applicant could only be appointed to a full-time, permanent contract if the worker had previously held a full-time position. Consequently, she was appointed to the full-time post but on a temporary contract. Although the less favourable treatment is easy to identify, there was no comparable full-time worker with which she could compare herself because no fulltime worker had applied for the position. According to Bell this illustrates the “benefits of the law permitting recourse to hypothetical comparators. In this case, it could be demonstrated that if a fulltime worker from within the enterprise had applied for the same position, the full-timer would have been appointed to a permanent contract.” Bell, Strengthening the protection, p. 12.

⁶⁹ M. Bell, ‘Between flexicurity and fundamental social rights: the EU Directives on atypical work’, *European Law Review*, vol. 37, no. 1, 2012, pp. 8, 9. In Case *Wippel*, Mrs Wippel, who was a shop worker, challenged an Austrian collective agreement. According to this collective agreement, a normal working week for full-time workers was set at 40 hours. It did not specify what constituted a normal working week for part-time workers. Mrs Wippel challenged this as less favourable treatment of part-time workers and indirect sex discrimination, given that 90% of part-time workers were women. The claimant was employed under an ‘on demand’ contract where no regular working hours were guaranteed and the volume of work fluctuated. She claimed that this constituted less-favourable treatment in comparison with full-time workers who, according to national law, had to have an agreed set of working hours. A preliminary issue that arose at the Court of Justice was whether her employment relationship qualified her as a ‘worker’ for the purposes of gender equality legislation and the Framework Agreement. The Court held that the claimant did fall within the scope of EU gender equality legislation, but that whether she was covered by the Framework Agreement was a matter for the national law.

situation creates the risk of a new dichotomy between those who are by Countouris called „typified-atypical“⁷⁰ and those who are according to Eurofound’s definition „very atypical“ workers^{71, 72}

However, locating an actual comparator is not enough in establishing less favourable treatment, while the claimant will have to demonstrate that the less favourable treatment is based on the ground that the worker is a part-time worker. This is the so-called “solely” test. If the employer can prove that there were other reasons which satisfy less favourable treatment, this test cannot be applied. It is worth mentioning that in the case of Part-Time Directive the latter test is very difficult to reconcile with indirect discrimination that, by its nature, concerns rules and practices applied in an abstract manner, and resulting in a particular disadvantage for a particular group.

There is another obstacle to proving less favourable treatment of part-time worker. The employer can show that this kind of treatment is „justified on objective grounds“, i.e. that the measure was an appropriate and necessary means of achieving a legitimate objective.

3.2. Access to part-time work

The Preamble of the ILO Convention underlines the economic importance of part-time work, as well as the need for employment policies to take into account its role in facilitating new employment opportunities. The increasing of employment by expanding part-time work could be achieved through different measures of deregulation as recommended in Article 9, if the existing labour laws and regulations prevent or discourage part-time work.⁷³ The Court of Justice has dealt with restrictions on those forms of work that deviate from the standard (full-time) employment contract, as initially imposed in some European legal systems.⁷⁴ In the case of *Michaeler*, which concerned an Italian law requirement that copies of all part-time employment contracts had to be sent to the La-

The Court decided that there were no comparable full-time workers in the enterprise, and that the full-time workers are obliged to perform work required under their contract, whereas casual workers had the possibility to decline work. The absence of comparable full-time worker meant there was no reason to proceed beyond the examination of her treatment, which effectively deprives casual workers of any opportunity to benefit from the principle of equal treatment. Case C-313/02 *Wippel* [2004] ECR I-9483.

⁷⁰ N. Countouris, *The changing law of the employment relationship – comparative analyses in the European context*, Aldershot, Ashgate, 2007, p. 89.

⁷¹ Eurofound, *Very Atypical Work: Exploratory Analysis of fourth European Working Conditions Survey*, cited in M. Bell, *Between flexicurity*, p. 31-48.

⁷² Bell, *Between flexicurity*, p. 41.

⁷³ Bell, *Strengthening the protection*, p. 12.

⁷⁴ Countouris, p. 88.

bour and Social Security Inspectorate, the opinion of the Court of Justice was that this was an unjustified restriction on part-time work that breached the Framework Agreement.⁷⁵

One of the objectives of the Directive is promoting flexible organization of working time. Therefore, the Directive is not simply an instrument that altruistically deals with the disadvantages of part-time workers, but is expressly designed as an instrument of employment policy aiming to increase part-time work in order to raise the employment rate, and stimulate a reform of the labour market.⁷⁶

A more complex problem in the labour market concerns the issue of access to (good quality) part-time work. The concentration of part-time work in low-paid, low-status occupations implies a structural inequality that cannot be addressed by the legal rules that guarantee to part-time workers the equal treatment as to full-time workers. According to Bell employers often restrict part-time work to positions at the lower grades in the enterprise and advertise managerial jobs on a full-time basis only. The latter practice does not seem to contravene the Convention's requirements. The possibility of adapting the employment contract to switch between full-time and part-time working or *vice versa* may be at the initiative of the worker or the employer. The employer could request the switch (to part-time work) with the aim of reducing salary costs for the enterprise, or a reorganisation of the business that requires full-time work.⁷⁷

According to Article 10 of the Convention the transfer from full-time to part-time work or *vice versa* should be voluntary, in accordance with national law and practice. The Recommendation encourages employers to take practical measures to facilitate such transfers (Art. 18). Also, in Art. 19 and 20 it recommends two worker's rights. Worker's refusal to transfer from one form of working to another (unless there are other operational requirements) should not be a valid reason for termination of employment contract. Workers with caring responsibilities should be able to transfer from full-time to part-time work (and back again). Due to different interests of the worker and employer, it is obvious that the balance between flexibility and security is difficult to strike.⁷⁸

Clause 5 of the Directive contemplates situations that concern access to part-time work. First, it requires from Member States and social partners to review and eliminate obstacles to part-time work („where appropriate"). Second, the employers have a duty to

⁷⁵ Cases C-55/07 and C-56/07 Michaeler, Subito GmbH, and Volgger v Amt für sozialen Arbeitsschutz, Autonome Provinz Bozen [2008] ECR I-3135.

⁷⁶ Bell, *Achieving the objectives*, p. 255, 265.

⁷⁷ Bell, *Strengthening the protection*, p. 12, 13.

⁷⁸ The worker would like to enjoy the flexibility to transfer from full-time and part-time employment, accompanied by security that the change of working time will not occur against his/her wishes. Employers would prefer flexibility in ordering those working time arrangements that best fit the requirements of the business, and the security that the worker can be returned to full-time status when necessary for the enterprise. Bell, *Strengthening the protection*, p. 13.

consider the request of the worker to transfer from full-time to part-time work (and *vice versa*). Thirdly, employers should also facilitate access to part-time work at all levels of the enterprise, including vocational training for part-time workers.

The progressive elimination of discriminatory requirements for access to particular conditions of employment and of other obstacles limiting opportunities for part-time work put an obligation on Member States to act for the removal of discriminatory laws and practices, both on their own initiative, in order to comply with European law and following individual complaints. Thereof, the Member States and the social partners, in their respective sphere of competence, have to identify and review obstacles which are likely to limit opportunities for part-timers. 'The non-binding nature of this clause creates uncertainties as regards a clear definition of a right to access to employment free of discrimination.'⁷⁹

According to Clause 5(3)(a) employers should, as far as possible, give consideration to workers' requests to transfer from full-time to part-time work 'that becomes available in the establishment'. Bell assesses the wording of this obligation as 'ambiguous'. If interpreted narrowly 'it would only cover situations where a part-time vacancy has arisen and fortuitously a full-time worker seeks to avail of that opportunity'. As the objective of the Framework Agreement is bolder, i.e. the flexible organisation of working time, the obligation should be given a broad interpretation, that 'full-time worker should be entitled to make such a request if the *possibility* of working part-time exists within the establishment.'⁸⁰

In the European Union there are a range of different approaches to regulating transfers between full-time and part-time work.⁸¹ The provisions of German *Law on part-time*

⁷⁹ Schiarra, *New Discourses*, 2011, p. 25, 26.

⁸⁰ Bell, *Achieving the objectives*, p. 273.

⁸¹ In United Kingdom, section 80F of the Employment Rights Act (ERA) 1996 provides a right to request a change in the terms and conditions of employment, including in relation to the hours and times of work. This includes a request to change from full-time to part-time working. The right to request is extended to a qualifying employee if 'his purpose in applying for the change is to enable him to care for someone' (s. 80F(1)(b) ERA 1996.). This right covers parents with children under the age of 17 (or 18 if the child is disabled), and carers of persons over the age of 18 where the employee is married to, in a civil partnership with, or is a relative of the person receiving care (Regs 3A-3B, *The Flexible Working (Eligibility, Complaints and Remedies) Regulations 2002*, SI 2002/3236.) According to academic literature this right seems to be more procedural than substantive. D. McCann, *Regulating flexible work*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2008, p. 91; G. James, *The legal regulation of pregnancy and parenting in the labour market*, London, Routledge Cavendish, 2009, p. 48, in Bell, *Achieving the objectives*, p. 274. The employer must comply with certain rules prescribing the handling of the request (e.g. a possibility to appeal against the initial decision). If the request is refused, the employer's reason must fall into one of a list of specified reasons (s.80G(1)(b) ERA 1996.). The role of the Employment Tribunal is limited to whether a request was handled according to the statutory requirements and not based on incorrect facts (s.80H(1) ERA 1996.). The Tribunal may not evaluate the merits of the employer's decision, provided it falls within the list of permitted reasons for refusing the request. There are different opinions on the utility of this right in literature. For more see H. Collins,

work and fixed-term employment contract are a good example of a law that guarantees the worker effective way to achieve a transfer from full-time to part-time work. The right to request working part-time was introduced in 2001 for employees with more than six months' continuous service and where the employer regularly employs more than 15 employees (regardless of the number of trainees, employed by the same employer). The employer has a duty to discuss the request with the employee in order 'to reach an agreement' ('Vereinbarung'). The employer has a possibility to refuse the reduction in working time for 'operational reasons' (i.e. when the reduction of working time can cause a serious damage to the work organisation, the course of work or the security in the enterprise, or the unproportionate costs).⁸²

Compared to the German legislation, the Croatian legislation is lagging far behind, as shall be seen in the following part.

IV. PART-TIME WORK IN CROATIA

What is the state of play in Croatia concerning the obligations prescribed by the Directive? Analysing the rights of part-time workers in Croatian law, it is evident that in line with (the prohibition of discrimination prescribed by) the Directive Croatian Labour Act⁸³ guarantees: right to equal pay and other material rights of part-time workers (according to *pro rata temporis* principle); equivalent conditions for vocational training and education; right to rest and right to paid annual leave; and in general, the same working conditions as for comparable full-time workers. Legal scholars find that the level of statutory protection of part-time workers is much higher than the level guaranteed by the Directive and that this is the reason why part-time work in Croatia is only of marginal importance.⁸⁴ However, in respect of the Directive's objective to promote part-time work,

'The right to flexibility' in J. Conaghan and K. Rittich (eds.), *Labour law, work, and family*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2005, p. 99, 119-120. The employees' requests are often accepted in practice, and more frequently in respect of female employees. Therefore, the right to request flexible working covers only a limited group of employees. Bell, *Achieving the objectives*, p. 274. Other states have introduced stronger legal provisions concerning the right of the employee to move to part-time work.

⁸² § 8 Teilzeit- und befristungsgesetz vom 21. Dezember 2000 (BGBl. I S. 1966), das zuletzt durch Artikel 23 des Gesetzes vom 20. Dezember 2011 (BGBl. I S. 2854) geändert worden ist (Law on Part-time Employment Contract and Fixed-term Employment Contracts). For more see M. Schmidt, 'The right to part-time work under German law: progress in or a boomerang for equal employment opportunities', *Industrial Law Journal*, vol. 30, 2001, pp. 335, 340; M. Fuchs, 'Germany: part-time work – a bone of contention' in S. Sciarra et al. (eds.), *Employment policy and the regulation of part-time work in the European Union*, New York, Cambridge University Press, 2004, p. 121.

⁸³ Zakon o radu, *eng.* Labour Act (Official Gazette 149/14)

⁸⁴ Ž. Potočnjak, 'Fleksigurnost radnih odnosa u Hrvatskoj i pravna stečevina Europske unije', *Zbornik Susreta pravnika Opatija '13*, J. Barbić and M. Giunio (eds.), Zagreb, Hrvatski savez udruga pravnika u gosp-

we can paraphrase Bell and say that the Croatian legislator took the half-hearted approach to flexible working.⁸⁵

4.1. Definition of part-time work

According to the Labour Act, full working time in Croatia amounts to 40 hours a week. The Labour Act defines part-time ('nepuno radno vrijeme') in relation to full time as "every working time that is shorter than full working time" (Art. 62/1). It can, therefore, amount to only one hour per week.

Specific duration of full-time work in an enterprise can be regulated by special law(s), collective agreements or in an agreement between the workers' council and the employer or in an employment contract (Art. 61/2). Therefore, not only do the employer and worker have to stipulate working hours in the employment contract, but also specify whether these should be considered full or part working time.

In addition, the contractual parties have to specify weekly and daily working hours.⁸⁶ Part-time workers perform their work according to the schedule of working hours ("raspored radnog vremena")⁸⁷ that depends on the stipulated number of working hours and the distribution of work on one or more days, or 6 days a week etc.

The fact that the Croatian legislator considers part-time work as an exception not in favor of the worker, could be seen from the perspective of the provisions of the Act (Art. 62) regulating the criteria for the accumulation of two or more part-time employment contracts of one worker. First, if part-time worker is employed by two or more employers her/his working time is limited and should not exceed 40 hours per week. However, even the worker whose total part time amounts to 40 hours per week by two or more employers, could sign another employment contract with another employer for the maximum of 8 working hours per week, or 180 working hours per year, provided she/he has a consent from the other employers.

In any case, a part-time worker who wants to conclude an employment contract with a second (or third) employer, has to inform this employer about the existing employment contract(s). Even though not prescribed by the Act, it seems logical and necessary that workers have a duty to inform their first employer too. Because of the particularities of

odarstvu, 2013, p. 309.

⁸⁵ M. Bell, *Achieving the objective*, p. 278.

⁸⁶ V. Jelčić, 'Radno vrijeme', in Ž. Potočnjak (ed.), *Radni odnosi u Republici Hrvatskoj*, Zagreb, Pravni fakultet u Zagrebu i Organizator, 2007, p. 171.

⁸⁷ The working time schedule could be agreed by employment contract, but also by collective agreement, or prescribed in regulation, employer's rules or by unilateral employer's decision (art. 66 LA). M. Zuber, 'Radna i socijalna prava zaposlenih u nepunom radnom vremenu u Hrvatskoj', *Revija za socijalnu politiku*, vol. 13, no. 1, 2006, p. 178-179.

this type of labour relations, the rights and duties of both part-time worker and their employers should be clear and precise in order to enable the fulfilment of rights and organization of work. Therefore, the authors propose *de lege ferenda* clarification to the provision in question.

The above mentioned statistics on the number of part-time workers employed by two or more employers in order to achieve full-time employment confirm that part-time work in Croatia is prevalently involuntary.

The new LA has resolved some doubts concerning the question whether work performed by the part-time worker above the contractually stipulated working hours represents overtime work or not. According to the LA, overtime work is every work a worker has to perform in case of force majeure or extraordinary increase of work load and in similar cases of necessity, based on a written request of employer, or when employee works longer than his full time or part time working hours. (Art. 65).

4.2. Right to equal pay and other material rights

The introduction of the *pro rata temporis* principle as regards the right to equal pay and other material rights of part-time workers is a novelty of the Labour Act of 2014. It took off the financial burden from the employer who is no more obligated to pay off to the part-time worker the same, i.e. full amount as to the full-time worker in case of different material rights.⁸⁸ Nevertheless, the Labour Act allows for derogations from the *pro rata temporis* principle, provided this is stipulated by collective agreements, employer's rules or by an individual employment contract.

Pursuant to the Labour Act, "other material rights" include the seniority award, compensation for annual leave, Christmas bonus and other rights. These rights are often regulated by collective agreements and employer's rules. Compensation for annual leave prescribed by collective agreements as a special annual reward paid by the employer was usually paid in an absolute amount to all workers irrespective of the individual worker's wage.

The right to paid travel expenses as an important material right is usually provided by collective agreements in full amount for part-timers as for workers working full time. Given the different purpose of this material right as compared to the compensation for annual leave or Christmas bonus, and considering its relatively high total amount, the right to a full amount of travel expenses seems to be one of the decisive issues for a worker who is willing to work part-time to accept this type of work.

Concerning possible derogations of the *pro rata temporis* principle, in collective agreements, employer's rules or individual employment contract those derogations should be

⁸⁸ Certainly, it doesn't include the right to a monthly wage, as well as the right to a minimum wage, and a wage compensation in case of absence because of illness, all counted based on the *pro rata temporis* principle.

explicitly prescribed.⁸⁹ It must be noted that the employer's and worker's duty to obligatory social insurance contributions and taxes are calculated in relation to the amount of gross wage. The contributions and taxes for part-time worker are proportionally lower to those for the full-time worker, wherefore they do not represent an additional burden for the Croatian employer.

4.3. Presumption of full-time work

If any right arising from employment relationship is based on a period of previous employment with the same employer, there is an irrefutable statutory presumption that the period of part-time work is a period of full-time work employment (Art. 62/5 LA). The most important examples of such rights are right to a statutory (minimum) period of notice and to redundancy payment in case of dismissal. In both cases, the amount of the wage (or wage compensation) and amount of redundancy payment are counted according to *pro rata temporis* principle.

4.4. A guarantee of the same working conditions

In addition to the already mentioned rights, the Labour Act prescribes a general duty of the employer to guarantee a part-time worker the same working conditions as to a comparable worker (Art. 63). In this case a criterion of an actual comparator is used.

The comparator is a worker who has an employment contract for a full-time work with the same employer, or another linked employer, and who has equal or similar professional knowledge and capabilities and who performs equal or similar work (Art. 63/1 LA). If no actual comparator exists, the duty of the employer is to guarantee a part-time worker the working conditions as prescribed in collective agreement or other regulation that the employer is obligated to apply and that are applicable to a full-time worker who performs similar work and has similar professional knowledge and capabilities. If such rules do not exist, the employer is obliged to guarantee adequate working conditions as to his full-time worker performing similar work and possessing similar professional knowledge and capabilities.

The duty of the employer is to guarantee part-time workers the same conditions for professional training and education as to full-time workers.

⁸⁹ Adapting the employer's rules will be easier than the provisions of the collective agreements. D. Čavrak, et. al. (eds), *Detaljni komentar novoga Zakona o radu*, Zagreb, Radno pravo, 2014, p. 223.

4.5. Access to part-time work

Clause 5 of the Directive requires the elimination of obstacles to part-time work. Croatian law does not entail any provisions regulating (at least generally) the duty to an active role of the state, social partners or individual employers in removing the obstacles to part-time work. Also, at the moment, we are not aware of the existence of these obstacles within Croatian law.

Furthermore, under Art. 62/7 of LA the employer is obligated to consider the request of the worker for change in the duration of working hours agreed by the employment contract: from part-time to full-time and *vice versa*.

However, the employer has this obligation only if a possibility for that type of work in his enterprise actually exists. It is important to note that the wording of the provision is not precise, and consequently the employer's obligation remains unclear and vague. Therefore, we are sceptical in regard to the effectiveness of this provision.⁹⁰

In light of these considerations it seems that much more has to be done in the Croatian legislation, and in policy to reach the objective envisaged by clause 5(3) of the Directive, namely promotion of part-time work by facilitating part-time work within the labour market, including flexibility for workers to move between part-time and full-time work.⁹¹ It should also be mentioned that the job-sharing scheme, as a special case of part-time work, has been offered through different packages of state aid for employment.⁹²

When analysing the constraints in the use of part-time working arrangements it should be borne in mind that as far as flexicurity is concerned the economic, social and labour market reform processes in Croatia during the last decade have not been driven by the guiding principles of flexicurity. One of the critical issues in this respect is an underdeveloped social partnership (social dialog) that has to overcome many barriers, most notably mutual distrust⁹³.

On the other hand, the access to paid work for women could be achieved through:

⁹⁰ In academic literature depicted as a „good but only instructive provision that doesn't impose any obligation to the employer“. Čavrak et al., p. 224.

⁹¹ Cf. M. Bell, *Achieving the objective*, p. 254.

⁹² S. Laleta and V. Smokvina, 'Državne potpore za zapošljavanje u svjetlu Opće uredbe o skupnim izuzećima i iskustava država članica EU', *Zbornik Pravnog fakulteta Sveučilišta u Rijeci*, vol. 32, no. 1, 2011., pp. 407-442.

⁹³ As Wilthagen and Tros put it: 'Trust is a major factor here. If levels of trust are low or absent, either among social partners or towards the government, flexicurity strategies can be expected to meet with strong opposition and mistrust ...countries, sectors and companies that lack a tradition and platform for coordination and negotiation seem to be at a disadvantage when it comes to producing flexibilitysecurity trade-offs'. T. Wilthagen and F. Tros, 'The concept of "Flexicurity": A new approach to regulating employment and labour markets', *Flexicurity paper 2003-4*, Tilburg University, 2004., <http://www.nvf.cz/assets/docs/80401adfb0953f74d581d0c0a71ff37/359-0/youth-flexicurity.pdf>, (accessed 5 October 2015).

1. childcare and elderly care (increase of funding for childcare and care for other dependants; providing incentives to companies for building and maintaining childcare facilities; providing support to employers who offer their employees career breaks; child care and other family support services; more liberal conditions for private child care services⁹;
2. flexibility - despite the debate of long-term consequences of part time work for gender equality, there is a need for promotion of flexible working arrangements that allow for a better reconciliation of work and family life in the form of flexible working hours, flexible workplace and flexible work contracts.

V. „VERY ATYPICAL WORK“, CASUAL WORK

Another important issue has surfaced, namely whether casual work should be treated as falling within the scope of part-time work.⁹⁴

Different studies carried out by the *Eurofound*⁹⁵ analyse the legal status of workers engaged in different ‘non-standard forms of work’, that have emerged in the European labour market. Within this broader category, the ‘very atypical’ forms of work have been developed involving ‘precarious situations’: workers with very short (six months or less) fixed-term contracts, zero hours or on-call working, non-written contracts, part-time work of fewer than 10 hours a week (‘mini-jobs’).⁹⁶

Not all of these ‘very atypical’ forms of work are necessarily equivalent to part-time work, but it seems likely that these categories of workers will often be working less than full-time hours.⁹⁷ According to the Eurofound research agriculture, food industry, personal care and cleaning industries, domestic services sectors, real estate sectors, education, health and social work sectors, and construction are the most common areas for ‘very atypical’ work, although overall only 2% of employees said that they worked less than 10 hours per week.⁹⁸

⁹⁴ The Court of Justice has adopted a fairly expansive definition of ‘worker’ that brings casual forms of work within the scope of various aspects of EU law, such as the right to work in another Member State or equal pay for women and men. *Countouris*, pp. 172-181.

⁹⁵ European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions, *Very atypical work*, cit.; European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions, *Flexible forms of work: ‘very atypical’ contractual arrangements*, Dublin, 2010.

⁹⁶ Eurofound, *Flexible forms of work*, pp. 3ff.

⁹⁷ Bell, *Strengthening the protection*, p. 8.

⁹⁸ Eurofound, *Very atypical work*, p. 9; Eurofound, *Flexible forms of work*, p. 10.

As previously mentioned, the Member States can exclude this category of workers from the scope of the ILO Convention 175. But even if this is not the case, the requirement of comparability makes the protection of their rights difficult. In addition, the EU Framework Agreement permits Member States after consulting social partners to ‘exclude wholly or partly from the terms of this Agreement part-time workers who work on a casual basis.’⁹⁹ Again, even in cases where casual workers were not excluded from the scope of the Framework Agreement, “its provisions may be of limited assistance”,¹⁰⁰ as in the above cited case *Wippel*.

In relation to the Part-time Work Directive, the Member States have become more intensively involved in the special regulation of part-time work, pursuing the following objectives: worker protection, employment promotion and flexibilisation of work relations; encouragement of part-time work and moderation of its relation to full-time work; regulation by soft and hard law.¹⁰¹

VI. PART-TIME WORK IN THE CASE LAW OF THE COURT OF JUSTICE OF THE EUROPEAN UNION (CJEU)

As Ellis pointed out, the case law settled before the Court of Justice of the European Union illustrates a tendency in labour law and social security regimes to exclude the workers whose working hours are low.¹⁰² The prerequisite for this is the existence of “thresholds, in terms of working hours or salary, in order to come within the scope of employment protection legislation (e.g. protection from dismissal) or for entitlement to social security benefits (e.g. unemployment allowance, sick pay).”¹⁰³ There are different national practices in this context.¹⁰⁴

⁹⁹ Clause 2(2).

¹⁰⁰ Bell, *Strengthening the protection*, pp. 8, 9.

¹⁰¹ P. Davies and M. Freedland, ‘The Role of EU Employment Law and Policy’ in S. Schiarra, P. Davies and M. Freedland (eds.), *Employment Policy and the Regulation of Part-time Work in the European Union (A Comparative Analysis)*, New York, Cambridge University Press, 2011, p. 71.

¹⁰² E. Ellis, *EU Anti-Discrimination Law*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2005, pp. 91-96.

¹⁰³ Bell, *Strengthening the protection*, p. 4.

¹⁰⁴ The German legislation limited an early retirement scheme to workers who had worked fulltime for three of the previous five years (Case C-77/02 *Steinicke v Bundesanstalt für Arbeit* [2003] ECR I-9027); part-time workers were excluded from membership of occupational pension schemes in Germany (Case 170/84 *Bilka-Kaufhaus GmbH v Weber Von Hartz* [1986] ECR 1607; and in United Kingdom (Case C-78/98 *Preston and others v Wolverhampton Healthcare NHS Trust and others* [2000] ECR I-3201); German legislation required employers to pay workers for a period of up to six weeks when the worker is on sick leave, but this did not apply to workers who worked less than 10 hours per week or 45 hours per month (Case 171/88 *Rinner-Kuhn v FWW Spezial-Gebaudereinigung GmbH & Co KG* [1989] ECR

There is only a limited body of case law under the Part-time (as well as fixed-term) Directive. For the purpose of this study hereinafter are analysed three cases.

In the Case *Mascellani*,¹⁰⁵ the Italian court (Tribunale di Trento) issued a preliminary question concerning the interpretation of Clause 5.2 of the Agreement implemented by the Part-time Work Directive 97/81/EC. This Clause reads as follows: “A worker’s refusal to transfer from full-time to part-time work or vice-versa should not in itself constitute a valid reason for termination of employment, without prejudice to termination in accordance with national law, collective agreements and practice, for other reasons such as may arise from the operational requirements of the establishment concerned.”

The request for a preliminary ruling has been made in proceedings between Ms Mascellani and the Ministero della Giustizia (Ministry of Justice) concerning a decision ordering the conversion of her part-time employment relationship into a full-time employment relationship. The applicant, Teresa Mascellani, was an employee of the Italian Ministry of Justice, working at the Court in Trento on a part-time basis, spread over 3 days a week. She worked part-time since 28 October 2000. Under Article 16 of Italian Law No 183, the public administration may, within 180 days of the entry into force of Law No 183/2010 and subject to the principles of fairness and good faith, re-evaluate decisions permitting the conversion of full-time employment relationships into part-time employment relationships where such decisions were adopted prior to the entry into force of the Decree-Law No 112 of 2008. The Ministry of Justice re-examined part-time arrangements granted to the applicant and, in accordance with the mentioned Article 16 of Law No 183, unilaterally terminated that arrangement by imposing a full-time working arrangement spread over six days (decision effective as of 1 April 2011). On 16 March 2011 Ms Mascellani informed the Ministry of Justice that she opposed the conversion of the part-time arrangement into a full-time employment. By a new decision (of 21 March 2011) the District Court in Trento ordered the applicant to comply with the new working arrangements. The applicant brought an action before the Ordinary Court in Trento seeking an annulment of the above mentioned decisions of the Ministry of Justice and the District Court in Trento. She argued that part-time working enables her to use her free time to care for her family and undertake vocational training.

2743); a provision of German law that part-time work would only be counted as two-thirds of normal working hours when calculating the length of service of workers (length of service was relevant to the possibility for promotion) (Case C-1/95 Gerster v Freistaat Bayern [1997] ECR I-5253); a provision of a German collective agreement for public sector employees that an annual bonus of one month’s extra salary was not payable to those working less than 15 hours per week (Case C-281/97 Krüger v Kreiskrankenhaus Ebersberg [1999] ECR I-5127); a provision of a German Federal civil service collective agreement restricting severance payments to those who worked at least 38 hours per week (Case C-33/89 Kowalska v Freie und Hansestadt Hamburg [1990] ECR I-2591).

¹⁰⁵ Case C-221/13 Teresa Mascellani v Ministero della Giustizia [2013].

The ECJ ruled that the Framework Agreement on part-time work, in particular Clause 5.2 thereof, must be interpreted as meaning that, in circumstances such as those in the main proceedings, it does not preclude national legislation pursuant to which the employer may order conversion of a part-time employment relationship into a full-time employment relationship without the consent of the worker concerned.

In a recent case *Österreichischer Gewerkschaftsbund v Verband Österreichischer Banken*¹⁰⁶ the Austrian trade union in the banking sector initiated proceedings before the Austrian Supreme Court against the employers' representatives in the banking sector. The issue at hand was that part-time workers falling within the scope of the applicable collective agreement in the banking sector ("bank staff and bankers") were entitled to only an amount of 'dependent child allowance' which was calculated *pro rata* on the number of hours worked. The 'dependent child allowance' is a social benefit paid by the employer to meet part of the employee's expenses for the maintenance of his/her child. The trade union held that the use of the principle of *pro rata temporis* as is laid down in the Directive on Part-time Work (Clause 4.2.) was not appropriate with regard to this allowance.

The Austrian Supreme Court referred questions to the ECJ for preliminary ruling, asking whether the principle of *pro rata temporis* should be applied to this allowance based on the (appropriate) nature of that benefit. If this is the case, could the disadvantage suffered by part-time workers that results from making a reduction in their entitlement to the dependent child allowance in proportion to their shorter working hours be objectively justified under Clause 4.1 of the Framework Agreement? The third question referred to the ECJ was that if the *pro rata temporis* should not be applied and no objective justification could be given for its use, does Article 28 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union render invalid all the provisions of the collective agreement relating to that area (in this case, child allowance) if the national practice is to render invalid certain parts of the collective agreement when only a point of detail in the collective agreement breaches an EU law rule?

The ECJ observed that the dependent child allowance is not a benefit provided for by law and paid by the State, but is paid by the employer pursuant to a collective agreement. Therefore, it cannot be treated as a 'social security benefit' within the meaning of EC Regulation 883/2004 on the coordination of social security systems, even though its objectives are similar to those of certain benefits provided for by this Regulation. Nevertheless, the child allowance does constitute (a part of) 'pay' to the worker, and as such it is determined by the terms of the employment relationship agreed between the worker and the employer. Consequently, for part-time workers the calculation of the dependent child allowance in accordance with the principle *pro rata temporis* is objectively justified, within the meaning of Clause 4.1 of the Framework agreement on part-time work, as the ECJ

¹⁰⁶ Case C-476/12 *Österreichischer Gewerkschaftsbund v Verband Österreichischer Banken* [2012].

has already decided in other cases.¹⁰⁷ It was also deemed appropriate within the meaning of Clause 4.2, since the dependent child allowance as an advantage paid in cash to workers is therefore a divisible benefit.¹⁰⁸

The ECJ ruled that the Clause 4.2 of Directive 97/81/EC must be interpreted as meaning that principle *pro rata temporis* applies to the calculation of the amount of a dependent child allowance paid by an employer to a part-time worker pursuant to a collective agreement such as that applicable to the employees of Austrian banks and bankers. Therefore, there was no need to answer preliminary questions 1 and 2.

Finally, in the Case *Cachaldora Fernández v Instituto Nacional de la Seguridad Social (INSS), Tesorería General de la Seguridad Social (TGSS)*¹⁰⁹ the Spanish national social security institutions¹¹⁰ calculated the permanent invalidity pension of Ms Cachaldora Fernández taking into account the periods during which she did not pay contributions to the social security scheme relying on reduced contribution bases, as she had worked on a part-time basis during the period immediately preceding that contribution gap. The High Court of Justice in Galicia asked the ECJ whether such a procedure is contrary to Article 4 of Directive 79/7/EEC¹¹¹ and Clause 5(1)(a) of Directive 97/81/EC. The Court ruled that Directive 97/81/EC did not apply in this case. The Court has based its decision on the following arguments. The preamble of the Framework Agreement relates to the ‘employment conditions of part-time workers, recognising that matters concerning statutory social security are for decision by the Member States’. According to the ECJ case law the term ‘employment conditions’, within the meaning of the Framework Agreement, covers pensions which depend on an employment relationship between worker and the employer, and consequently, statutory social security pensions (determined less by that relationship than by considerations of social policy) are excluded.¹¹² In the present case the pension at issue was proved to be statutory social security pension and consequently could not be regarded as an ‘employment condition’. Therefore, it does not fall within the scope of the Framework Agreement. According to the Court “an interpretation of ‘obstacles of a legal ... nature’, as referred to in Clause 5(1)(a) of the Framework Agreement,

¹⁰⁷ Case C-229/11 and C-230/11 *Heimann and Toltschin* [2012], para. 34.

¹⁰⁸ See by analogy, Cases C-395/08 and C-396/08 *Bruno and Others* [2010], para. 34, Case C-268/06 *Impact* [2008], para. 116.

¹⁰⁹ Case C-527/13 *Cachaldora Fernández v INSS, TGSS* [2014] OJ C 9

¹¹⁰ National Institute of Social Security and Social Security General Fund.

¹¹¹ Article 4(1) of Directive 79/7/EEC must be interpreted as not precluding a rule of national law which provides that the contribution gaps existing within the reference period for calculating a contributory invalidity pension, after a period of part-time employment, are taken into account by using the minimum contribution basis applicable at any time, reduced as a result of the reduction coefficient of that employment, whereas, if those gaps follow full-time employment, there is no provision for such a reduction.

¹¹² Case C-385/11 *Elbal Moreno* [2012], para. 21.

under which Member States would be forced to adopt, outside the area of employment conditions, measures relating to a pension such as that at issue in the main proceedings” (before the Spanish High Court of Justice in Galicia), “would amount to imposing general social policy obligations on those Member States concerning measures that fall outside the scope of the Framework Agreement.”¹¹³

VII. MEASURES ENCOURAGING PART-TIME WORK

The labour market regulation tended to encourage the growth of part-time work and introduce measures to improve its quality. Many governments have introduced various measures to facilitate or encourage part-time work, especially in countries with a high unemployment rate. Some of these promotional measures target discrimination of part-time workers in comparison to full-time workers and reduce the fixed costs associated with part-time employment. They consist in attenuating administrative barriers and targeting income tax issues, social security systems, unemployment benefits, job-sharing, career prospects and vocational training,¹¹⁴ as well as specific categories of workers, e.g. those with family responsibilities or older workers,¹¹⁵ or those with disability or certain illnesses, as a way of a reasonable accommodation.

A group of measures directly addresses the cost of part-time work, either generally or as a means of providing access to a labour market to new entrants. They consist in subsidies for part-time employment through tax relief or reduced social security contributions. In addition to their positive effects, they can give rise to an increase of proportion of involuntary part-time workers, i.e. underemployment.

The regulatory and institutional framework varies considerably across countries of the EU. Some regulations have a direct effect on the rate of part-time work. They are legally binding and limit the use of part-time work, i.e. the employer has the right to deny an employee’s request to work part-time.¹¹⁶ The second set of regulations has an indirect

¹¹³ Judgment of the Court, 14 April 2015, par. 39. Moreover the provision of Spanish law does not affect all part-time workers, but a group of them who had a gap in their contributions immediately after a period of part-time work. Therefore, the Court thinks that this provision, due to the random nature of the impact of that provision on part-time workers, cannot be regarded as a legal obstacle likely to limit the opportunities for part-time work. (par. 40).

¹¹⁴ Measures such as extension of social security coverage to part-timers or measures that depend on annual rather than weekly working hours affect employers. These measures are aimed at bringing the entitlements to social benefits for part-time workers in line with those of full-time workers. Bastelaer et al., p. 5.

¹¹⁵ Bollé, cit.

¹¹⁶ Certain types of regulation Also, V. Genre et al., ‘A widening scope for non wage components in collective bargaining in the EU?’ in: G. Fagan, J. Morgan and F. P. Mongelli (eds.), *Institutions and wage formation in the New Europe*, Cheltenham, Edward Elgar, 2003, pp.134-173.

effect on part-time employment through different financial incentives for firms to offer part-time work as well as for employees to accept it.¹¹⁷ A third set of regulations and institutions influence employment in general, but may have an indirect impact on part-time employment too.¹¹⁸ Those provisions belong to the child benefit/care system and unemployment benefit systems. Both may create an ‘unemployment trap’.¹¹⁹

Taking into account the previously said, it is obvious how difficult it is to influence the quantitative development of atypical part-time work. At a qualitative level that includes social rights, labour law, wage issues, there is more potential for political influence in terms of “context governance”.¹²⁰ In order to disconnect part-time work from precarious working and living conditions, the following policy measures could be proposed as the most essential:

- more employee-orientated flexibility;
- the right to change from full-time to part-time and *vice versa*;
- full inclusion in the social system and integration under labour law regulations;
- breaking down traditional role models; expansion of childcare institutions;
- reduction of overtime, working time and non-permanent working contracts; reducing the risks of future precarious conditions.¹²¹

The question thus arises as to whether the term “normal” should refer to any relations to traditional working patterns? A possible answer is that “normal” should be used for

¹¹⁷ Labour laws may facilitate the conversion of full-time jobs into voluntary part-time employment with the aim of reconciling personal and professional lives. J. Ginn and S. Arber, ‘How does part-time work lead to low pension income’, in O’Reilly and Fagan (eds.), *Part-time prospects*, pp. 156–174.

¹¹⁸ G. Laroque and B. Salanié, “Participation, Fertility and Financial Incentives in France”, Paper presented at ECB/CEPR workshop “What Explains the Pattern of Labour Supply in Europe”, Frankfurt, June 2003, cited in H. Buddelmeyer, G. Mourre and M. Ward, *The Determinants of Part-Time Work in EU Countries: Empirical Investigations with Macro-Panel Data*, IZA DP, no. 1361, 2004, p. 10, <http://repec.iza.org/dp1361.pdf>, (accessed 3 October 2015).

¹¹⁹ For mothers with young children it has been argued that the probability of (re-)entering the labour market, either in the form of full-time or part-time employment, is strongly linked with the system of child benefit/care arrangements in place. In general, the provision of child benefits can create an “unemployment trap” if benefits are means tested. Moreover, some child benefit systems grant additional income to parents who renounce work in order to take care of their young children. On the other hand, the lack of affordable (subsidized) childcare may represent a major disincentive to taking up employment. Similarly, unemployment benefit systems (together with other benefits) may create an ‘unemployment trap’ through high net replacement rates and long benefit duration.

¹²⁰ M. Fink, ‘Atypische Beschäftigungsverhältnisse und deren politische Steuerung im internationalen Vergleich’, *Österreichische Zeitschrift für Politikwissenschaft*, no. 39, 2004, pp. 401–415, cited in T. Hinterseer, ‘Part-time work: Atypical? Precarious? Normal?’, *European Journal of Futures Research*, 2013, <http://link.springer.com/article/10.1007%2F940309-013-0018-1/fulltext.html#CR37>, (accessed 5 September 2015).

¹²¹ Hinterseer, cit.

all working arrangements which guarantee a high amount of social security and individual freedom for employees. Flexible working time models need to adopt a more employee-friendly orientation with more time-autonomy and self-determination. To achieve this goal, flexibility must be managed and controlled politically.¹²² According to Rodgers, it is precisely this combination of institutions and policies which constitutes a social model, whereas an important lesson to be learned from successful experiences in Europe and elsewhere is that the broad participation and social dialogue in the process are of vital importance.¹²³

VIII. CONCLUSION

Part-time work has become an important instrument of the national legislators to create new jobs and to respond to employers' demands for increased flexibility. For workers it can be a „bridge“ between employment and inactivity and *vice versa*, as well as an instrument to achieve a better balance between working life and family responsibilities.

Since atypical employment, such as part-time work, is probably not going to be the first choice for the companies or for people looking for work, the interests of the parties involved are likely to differ, which can result in precariousness of this type of work. Consequently, the law regulating atypical employment relationship has a complex role to play today: the institutional framework should help to promote, or at least not hinder the creation of the desired voluntary part-time work arrangements and to put those workers on equal footing with „standard“ workers. Hence, the underlying principle should be their integration, not exclusion.

Recognising the advantages of part-time work for workers and employers, both the Convention and Directive have laid down the principle of non-discrimination of part-time workers and access to part-time work. The principle of non-discrimination as defined by the Directive includes the ban on less favourable treatment (in relation to a 'comparable full-time worker'), unless justified on objective grounds, and the recourse, where appropriate, to the principle of *pro rata temporis*. This principle has been shaped as a justiciable right.

Clause 5 on progressive elimination of discriminatory requirements for access to particular conditions of employment and other obstacles which may limit the opportunities for part-time work imposes the obligation to Member States to act in order to remove discriminatory laws and practice together with social partners, in their sphere of compe-

¹²² Hinterseer, cit.

¹²³ G. Rodgers, 'Labour Market Flexibility and Decent Work', *DESA Working Paper*, No. 47, 2007, http://www.un.org/esa/desa/papers/2007/wp47_2007.pdf, (accessed at 3 September 2015)

tence and through procedures prescribed in collective agreements. Contrary to the principle of non-discrimination, the Member States consider these provisions as non-binding. Consequently, in the absence of a clear definition in national legislations doubt is cast on the guarantee of individual rights of part-time workers. As Schiarra points out, it is an interesting but unclear combination of regulatory techniques and hard law principles in a soft law environment.

The Croatian legislator follows the same path. Although the Labour Act prescribes the right of the worker to request flexible working in line with the Directive, it neither requires from the state and social partners to remove the obstacles to part-time work, nor gives an enforceable guarantee to the worker to move from part-time to full-time work or *vice versa*, wherefore, new mechanisms *de lege ferenda* are needed. The obligation of the employer to consider the request of the worker to change from part-time to full-time should be defined more precisely. Considering the other side of the coin, policy-makers should do more in the implementation of different measures in order to facilitate part-time work within the labour market.

As is the case in other European countries, women work mostly as part-time workers in Croatia. The first problem is the misuse of certain flexible forms of work and at the same time underuse of other non-standard employment arrangements. The second problem is related to the lack of awareness that women are overrepresented in this kind of employment, not as a consequence of their will, but due to reduced workload or misuse of some forms of work, which means that they hold temporary, insecure or even informal jobs. In other words, women hold weaker positions in the labour market, which makes them more vulnerable to poverty and external shocks, such as the recent economic crisis.

The Croatian society must first and foremost strengthen institutional protection of women's rights, encourage the work of women's think-tank associations, develop atypical forms of employment contracts and undertake a transition from fixed to flexible working hours. Such an approach, coupled with changes to the educational policy, education of judges and labour inspectors in the domain of gender equality, as well as more intensive and more responsible role of the media, strengthening of labour courts and speeding up their activity can lead to a breaking down of stereotypes and achieving equal distribution of responsibilities in family and working environment, affirming the principles and values of equality as an inseparable part of individual's integrity in general.

As previously mentioned, part-time work has been observed as a phenomenon that belongs to the family-friendly labour environment, mostly reserved for women with family responsibilities, or as a means to enter or exit gradually from the labour market. However, it is vital to emphasize that it can also be a useful device for another vulnerable category of workers, namely those with disabilities or illnesses.

The ILO definition of five key dimensions for a proper working time include healthy, family friendly and productive working time, gender equality by working time and choice and influence regarding working time. For most of Europe's part-time workers, these goals are still far from achieved. Needless to say, in respect of part-time workers in Croatia much remains to be done as well.